

Collatz Conjecture and a related function: $(3x+1)/4$ vs $(3x+1)/2$

Madhukrx

7th May 2026

Consider the following recursive function:

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} n/4 & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{4} \\ (3n + T)/4 & \text{if } n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

Here n is a rational number:

$$n = \left(\frac{4a + b}{4c + d} \right)$$

$T \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $T \equiv -3b/d \pmod{4}$.

Comment 1: Why T is defined exactly like this will become clear in later part of this paper. The point to be noted here is that $n = \frac{4a + b}{4c + d}$ so when n is an integer the value of $4c + d = 1$; so c becomes 0 and d is equal to 1; thus value of T for integers is $k \in \{1, 2, 3\} = -3b \pmod{4}$

It's clear looking at this function that any natural number must decrease continuously after each step of this function; so any natural number must reach either 1,2,3 after a finite number of steps. While all negative integers will reach 0 after finite number of steps (this is not immediately obvious but a bit of basic arithmetic would lead us to it). Since the proof of this statement is trivial so I am not going to prove it here and leave it up to the reader. As for rational numbers any rational number of the form

$$\frac{Z}{3^C}$$

where Z and C are integers (I will represent numbers of this form as N from now on); will reach either a positive or negative integer after a few steps (because due to multiplication by 3 at each step, the denominator which is just a power of 3 will eventually become 1) and eventually through them it will reach 1,2,3 or 0. Why I am considering rational numbers of this particular form only is because this is what concerns us. And k is defined as $-3b/d$ because for rational numbers if T was defined otherwise then it would not work, and some rationals of the form $\frac{Z}{3^C}$ (or as I defined N) instead of going to 1,2,3 or 0 after finite steps will instead go to a infinitely divergent path.

0.1 comparative equations

Now I am going to post an equation here which some of you will immediately recognize as the precursor to Crandall's cycle formula which is also mentioned in Tao's work and which many amateurs like myself have derived. We can get the cycle formula from this equation if we make N and R equal.

$$N = \frac{2^m \cdot R - \sum_{i=0}^v 3^i \cdot 2^{c_i}}{3^{v+1}} \quad (1)$$

Here $c_0 > c_1 > c_2 > \dots c_i > c_{i+1} > c_v$ and $m > c_0$ and all these variables are natural numbers. Anyone who has worked out this equation themselves would know how these nuances come about. This equation tells us that for any collatz trajectory starting from N and leading to R this equation holds. Why the denominator is $v+1$ is because it must be 1 more than the maximum power of 3 relative to the

summation term in the numerator which I have set as v.

Now if we apply the same equation to the function $f(n)$ which I have defined above then we will get the following equation

$$N = \frac{2^{2l} \cdot R - \sum_{i=0}^u 3^i \cdot 2^{2k_i} \cdot T_i}{3^{u+1}} \quad (2)$$

Here $k_0 > k_1 > k_2 > \dots k_i > k_{i+1} > k_v$ and $l > k_0$ and all these variables are natural numbers.

Since this equation is derived from the $(3x+k)/4$ function instead of $(3x+1)/2$ so the 2s in equation 1 is replaced by 4s in equation 2 which I have expressed as 2^2 .

Also to account for different values of $k \in 1, 2, 3$ being added each step, (which was always 1 in case of $(3x+1)/2$; but in this case it can be 1,2 or 3 since we're talking mod 4 here.) I have added the variable T_i here which can take values 1,2 or 3 independently for each term.

I have smoothed out any errors or oversight which might occur when transforming one equation into another. If you still have some questions then feel free to ask.

For equation 2 it is clear (as I have argued previously) that any number of the form N will reach 0,1,2 or 3 and so equation 2 will hold for all such N even if we limit R to 1,2,3 and 0

And conversely if we limit R to integers only; then from the structure of the equation it's immediately obvious that we can only get numbers of the form N.

For equation 1 (which is just another way to write the collatz function applied multiple times) it is clear that any number of the form N will reach any integers and from there, there is the following possibilities:-

It could either go to

1 (in the 1,4,2,1 loop);

0 (on the 0,0,0 path example of N which goes to 0 is -1/3 or -5/9);

-1 (example: N = -2, -4 etc);

-5 (in the -5, -7,loop);

-17 (in the -17, -25... loop)

or it could go to any New divergent element (NDE) which we haven't found yet

or it could go to any New cycle element (NCE) which we haven't found yet

These are the only possibilities.

And so equation 1 will hold for all N even if we limit R to 1, -1, 0, -5, -17, NDE, NCE

And conversely if we limit R to integers only; then from the structure of the equation it's immediately obvious that we can only get numbers of the form N.

Another way to look at this whole thing is that we can consider equations 1 and 2 as functions acting on an integer R and a parity vector P (which decides the variables $landm, vandu, k_i and c_i$); then if we allow any string to be chosen as the parity vector, then all numbers of the form N are all the possible outputs. This is why I only talked about numbers of form N because I was only concerned with values the output of this function can take when R is an integer. And equations 1 and 2 hold for all values of form N.

0.2 Key takeaway point

For equation 1:- equation 1 will hold for all N even if we limit R to 1, -1, 0, -5, -17, NDE, NCE

:: and conversely all combinations of any integer R and any parity vector will only produce values in the range N.

For equation 2:- equation 2 will hold for all N even if we limit R to 1, 2, 3, 0 :: and conversely all combinations of any integer R and any parity vector will only produce values in the range N

0.3 Now we come to the slightly interesting results part

Consider equation 2 which is just a function of integer R (which is now limited to 1,2,3,0) and a parity vector P.

Now imagine for a second a specific form of equation 2 where we limited R to 1 and 2 only; and the parity vector could only comprise of a string of 1s and 0s (which would in turn mean that all T_i are 1). Then any such equation will automatically be in the form of equation 1 and 2 both with $R = 1$ or 2 and thus we would have shown that all N generated by such equations go to 1 or 2 under the collatz trajectory.

But the issue is that this accounts for a specific subset of N and not all N.

Now consider that instead of parity vector being composed of 1s and 0s only, it also contained 2s. Then T_i could take values of 1,2.

Now since

$$k_0 > k_1 > k_2 > \dots k_i > k_{i+1} > k_v \text{ and } l > k_0$$

and the exponents of 2 in the summand terms is $2k^i$ so multiplying any of the terms by 2 won't disrupt the order which is required for the equation to be in form of equation 1.

So even if N was generated from a parity vector that includes 0, 1, 2 then also equation 1 will hold for N and so it will go down to 1 or 2 under collatz trajectory. So we just expanded the subset of N for which the conjecture is true.

0.4 where I got stuck

So all the 2s as T_i kind of get absorbed neatly into equation 2 so that it looks like equation 1. But we haven't got rid of the 3s (which I can't)

Also since inputting $R = 0$ only gives out negative values which I am not interested in (but you might be) so I will limit R to 1, 2, 3 now; but since the 2 gets absorbed into 2l so just 1, 3. It's time to rewrite the equation 2 with all the inferences and changes

$$N = \frac{2^p \cdot H - \sum_{i=0}^u 3^i \cdot 2^{2j_i} \cdot H_i}{3^{u+1}} \quad (3)$$

It's exactly same as the equation 2 but

I have replaced R with H and T_i with H_i which can only take a value of 1 or 3.

I have replaced 2l and $2k_i$ with p and j_i to account for the 2 values which will be assimilated into the exponents and thus change them.

0.5 conclusion

1. There is little difference between an equation in the form of equation 3 and an equation in the form of equation 1 which is that in equation 3 there is a 3 attached to a few terms here and there. (Although this little difference might turn out to be huge pain in the ass as is the case with collatz).

2. What one needed to do to prove the collatz conjecture was to show that an equation in form of equation 1 exists for all natural numbers. While previously there was nowhere to start from, what I have shown that for a specific subset of numbers of form N (This subset includes all the natural numbers); the equation 3 holds always which is very similar to equation 1.

If someone could prove that equation 3 could always be transformed into equation 1 with any bounds on R at all - it will be huge

One way to proceed towards this would be to consider that in equation 3, for any summand A of the form $3^i \cdot 2^{k_i}$ in the numerator for which H_i is 3, we can express it as $2A + A$, we will consider this single A as error term and the 2A which is equal to $3^i \cdot 2^{k_i}$ will be transformed to $3^i \cdot 2^{k_i+1}$. Then we could take summation of all such error terms and then proceed in some way idk. One thing to note is that

sum of error terms is always going to be less than half of the total sum of all $3^i \cdot 2^{k_i}$ terms in the numerator

3. I have refined the idea of using $(an + b)/d$ like functions with different d for studying the colatz conjecture; which I hope might help some.

4. There are a few more interesting results if I fidget around with it but I just want to see if someone more learned than myself has got better tools or ideas to get something out of this.